

Review of: Open Science Project DMP - version 0 - Team Atreides
Revision notes

Erica Andreose* ¹, Leonardo Zilli², and Salvatore Di Marzo³

^{1,2,3} *University of Bologna, Italy*

Dear Editors,

We express our gratitude for the time and effort dedicated to the reviewing of our submitted DMP. We worked diligently to address all the concerns raised by the referees. Below we provide our detailed response to their comments. We hope that the applied revisions are to the satisfaction of the editors.

Kind regards,

Erica Andreose, on behalf of the authors

Manuscript information

Title: “Review of: Open Science Project DMP - version 0 - Team Atreides”

Authors: Leonardo Zilli, Erica Andreose, Salvatore Di Marzo

Revision: 1

DMP version 0 - old version: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10898482>

DMP version 1 - new version: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11152566>

*Corresponding author

✉ erica.andreose@studio.unibo.it

Reviewer 1 - <https://doi.org/10.32388/U63N7W>

Comment I (Reviewer 1):

The section concerning the dataset focuses on data already published elsewhere: it is an IRIS bibliographic data dump, and the authors did not filter those data in any way using other information.

Answer: We will add additional descriptions for the new data created during processing.

Assignment: Erica
Work in progress

Comment II (Reviewer 1):

I'm not sure if the DMP describes the new data that this research will produce.

Answer: The data used to achieve this research will nevertheless be stored in a repository accessible to the public. We will add these information in the future.

Assignment: Erica
Work in progress

Comment III (Reviewer 1):

All data will be assigned DOIs, but only the software will be provided with additional metadata.

Answer: We agree and we added the description of the dataset using metadata controlled by the DCAT vocabulary.

Assignment: Erica
Done

Reviewer 2 - <https://doi.org/10.32388/493F5X>

Comment IV (Reviewer 2):

A few things should be noted: about the possibility to assign outputs with persistent identifiers, to my knowledge, GitHub actually provides the option to obtain persistent identifiers (permalinks) for files in the repository.

Answer: Persistent identifiers (permalinks) for files in the repository will be added at the end of the data processing and analysis, along with links to the repository containing the data processing software.

Assignment: Erica
Work in progress

Reviewer 2

Comment V (Reviewer 2):

In future versions of the DMP, as the team gains a better understanding of the data, adding more metadata could help.

Answer: We agree and we added the description of the dataset using metadata controlled by the DCAT vocabulary.

Assignment: Erica
Done

Reviewer 2

Comment VI (Reviewer 2):

However, it could be clearer about the new data the project will create. Adding more details about what this data will be and how it relates to the research questions would be helpful.

Answer: We will add additional descriptions for the new data created during processing. We have included the research questions in the dedicated software section.

Assignment: Erica
Work in progress

Reviewer 2

Comment VII (Reviewer 2):

It would be beneficial to outline the new data the project will generate to address its research questions. Also, adding the research questions themselves to the overall description would provide valuable context for reviewers.

Answer: We have included the research questions in the dedicated software section. Description of the new data will be added in the future.

Assignment: Erica
Work in progress